

Women's financial Inclusion in Bangladesh: Assessing Inbuilt Challenges

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Abstract

The study strived to review the present status of women's financial inclusion, identify the key factors for ensuring effective financial services for women, and examine the relationship between financial inclusion and women empowerment in Bangladesh. It reveals that Female-headed households are not increasing significantly compared to other developing countries. Only 10% of women have full access, while 23% have partial access to financial services. 33% of women have bank accounts and 20% are empowered which means they can take part in the decision-making of their family. Women face a lot of inherent general challenges together with challenges originating from the supply side; regulatory and institutional framework; and social problems. The study recommends adopting a gender-sensitive financial inclusion policy. The existing regulatory and institutional framework should be updated to motivate women to be included in financial services. Financial education and financial literacy programs should be taken for rapid awareness and financial literacy building among women. Social inclusion of poor women is needed for their financial inclusion. Financing small businesses owned by women can improve women's social inclusion.

Keywords: Women's financial inclusion, gender-sensitive, women empowerment, social inclusion, financial literacy

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

It is well known that well-functioning financial systems are needed for the economic development of a country. It also covers purposes such as offering savings, payment, and risk management products to as large a set of participants as possible, and seeking out and financing good growth opportunities wherever they may be. The policymakers, practitioners and researchers have so far emphasized the efficiency and stability aspects of financial systems and ignored the broader access to financial services. However, the current development theories increasingly project the role of access to financial services, the lack of which is often the critical element underlying income inequality as well as slower growth. The concept of "Financial inclusion" has developed as a tool to achieve inclusive growth since 2005, the year that the UN announced the International Microcredit Year. The consensus is that financial inclusion may contribute to achieving economic growth and poverty reduction goals of any country. It will enable millions of low-income people to improve their economic and social status by participating in the formal financial system. The economic policy of every nation has underscored the significance of an inclusive financial system. The advantages of an inclusive financial system can hardly be exaggerated. Women's empowerment is one of the recent priority issues in developing countries since women have fewer salaried jobs. According to Mayoux (1998), empowerment is a multidimensional and intertwined method of change about power. Krishna (2003) stated that women's empowerment is a process through which women can make their choices and renovate these choices into desired actions and outcomes. Economically empowering women is indispensable both to apprehend women's rights and to achieve broader development goals such as economic growth, poverty reduction, and social welfare. According to Golla, Malhotra, Nanda, & Mehra (2011), when women can succeed and advance economically as well as have the power to make economic decisions, women are said to be economically empowered. While it is evident by researchers and scholars that women's economic empowerment promotes inclusive growth of a country.

1.2 Financial Inclusion

Financial Inclusion or inclusive financing is the delivery of services at affordable cost to sections of disadvantaged and low-income segments of society, where those services are not available or affordable. Access to responsibly delivered financial services means that people

can (a) Save money safely, with less risk or loss through fire, theft fraud, etc.(b) Send and receive money safely (c) Borrow for consumption or investment purposes based on an understanding of pricing, terms and conditions (d) Insure against risk. Financial inclusion (FI) has become a significant issue in developing countries like Bangladesh where a large number of people are still far from access to basic financial services and formal financial institutions. Here access to basic financial services remains a challenge for many, especially women, marginal farmers, informal sector enterprises and other socially excluded groups. Only 31% of the adult population has an account at formal financial institutions. If semi-formal and informal financial services are taken into account, the proportion of adults with access to financial services rises significantly to 79.25%. However, ensuring broad-based and inclusive economic growth continues to be a significant challenge for the government of Bangladesh (GOB), as in the case of many developing countries.

1.3 Women's Financial Inclusion

Roughly half of the population of Bangladesh is women. Women's financial inclusion occurs when women have effective access to a range of financial products and services that cater to their multiple business and household needs and that are responsive to the socio-economic and cultural factors that cause financial exclusion in men and women to have different characteristics. Women's Financial Inclusion refers to a state in which all age women, including those currently excluded by the financial system, have effective access to the financial services provided by formal institutions: credit, savings (defined broadly to include current accounts), payments, and insurance. Access to the financial system remains a challenge for the rural poor women in Bangladesh. Financial Inclusion, managed properly, can increase the empowerment of women in several ways. Firstly, having access to resources on their account and to the tools that help them earn a living can increase women's bargaining power within the household and their influence over how money and other resources are used. Secondly, financial inclusion can help increase women's opportunities to earn an income or control assets outside the household. Thirdly, it can reduce women's vulnerability by, for example, allowing them to insure against risk or borrow to meet unexpected expenses, such as medical treatment. They are all key factors for economic empowerment and they can also help to empower women more broadly. In rural areas, we find the popularity of mobile money transaction services but a large portion of the population especially village women remained out of banking services.

1.4 Empowerment

Empowerment means individuals acquiring the power to think and act freely, exercise choice, and fulfil their potential as full and equal members of society. Empowerment can be viewed as a "means of creating a social environment in which one can make decisions and make choices either individually or collectively for social transformation. It strengthens the innate ability by way of acquiring knowledge, power, and experience (Hashemi Schuler and Riley, 1996)". Empowerment is the process of enabling or authorizing individuals to think, autonomously take action, and control work. It is the process by which one can gain control over one's destiny and the circumstances of one's life. Empowerment includes control over resources (physical, human, intellectual, and financial) and ideology (beliefs, values, and attitudes). Women's empowerment is very essential for the development of society. There are some principles of women's empowerment. The [Women's Empowerment Principles](#) offer practical guidance to businesses and the private sector on how to empower women in the workplace, marketplace, and community. Developed through a partnership between UN Women and the [United Nations Global Compact](#), the principles are designed to support companies in reviewing existing policies and practices—or establishing new ones—to realize women's empowerment (Akter and Rahman 2018, Rahman 2021).

1.5 Women's Empowerment and Financial Inclusion

The strongest arguments for women's financial inclusion are economic: access to finance increases access to productive assets and increases productivity, and financial intermediation is linked to stronger economic growth. Access and usage of financial services are levers for increasing women's participation in the economy. For instance, International Finance Corporation (IFC) research shows that greater inclusion of women in the economy would allow gains in GDP between 2% and 3.5% in some cases. International Monetary Fund (IMF) research shows considerable evidence that when women can develop their full labour market potential, there can be significant macroeconomic gains. Better opportunities for women to earn and control income could contribute to broader economic development in emerging markets, such as higher levels of school enrolment for girls. Enhanced access to training and better support networks among female entrepreneurs also help to raise the productivity of enterprises owned and managed by women. Closing the credit gap for SMEs is a particularly promising avenue to increase economic growth and per capita incomes. It is estimated that, globally, over 70 percent of markets, with country contexts play a major role in determining

the linkages and trade-offs between financial inclusion, GDP, and equality. IMF research shows there is no one-size-fits-all policy prescription, but an important first step is developing an appropriate legal, regulatory, and institutional framework and a supportive environment.

Just as women play multiple roles as economic actors and caretakers of their families, women's financial inclusion has multiple benefits, both at the enterprise and household level. For women to invest in and grow their businesses, they need financial resources. They then tend to invest their financial resources in their homes, the nutrition and health of their families, the education of their children, and their communities. These investments in both enterprises and families can contribute to generational changes that lead to long-term prosperity and security.

Women may be slower to adopt financial services, but many studies have shown they transact more frequently and are inherent savers. Providing access to formal savings instruments allows women to increase consumption, which in turn benefits their families and increases productive investment. In developing countries, the gender gap in formal savings (an account at a financial institution where the client intends to save) is smaller than the gender gap in account ownership overall (access to an account at a financial institution), suggesting that women are more likely to use accounts to set aside money as savings.

Despite the macro and micro benefits of investing in women's financial inclusion, policymakers have not consistently integrated measures to address financial inclusion. A deep understanding, of the specific constraints low-income women face in accessing and using financial products and services, is necessary to create or design inclusive policy frameworks. Apart from this, the scenario of financial inclusion in Bangladesh is not so disappointing.

The services we discussed so far do not cover the range of issues that comprise a gender equity agenda, nor even the full range of issues that would be needed to address women's economic empowerment in its totality. The focus is on where financial inclusion, which embraces a much broader range of activities than traditional microfinance, overlaps with a wider gender equity and economic empowerment agenda, as in the diagram below:

Table 1: *Women's financial inclusions*

Micro Insurance	SME Finance
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Cash Transfers

Branchless Banking

Micro Finance

Banking policy

Reform

It is recognized that “the women’s market” represents numerous segments of women clients, from low-income self-employed women in the informal sector to women who work in agricultural value chains, to small- and medium-enterprise (SME) owners, to low-income salaried workers (factory workers, domestic workers, etc.). This report speaks about the rural unbanked and under-banked women.

1.6 Problem Statement

Access to the financial system remains a challenge for the rural poor women in Bangladesh. Mobile money transaction services are very popular in rural areas but an overwhelming proportion of the population remains unbanked. Women, in particular, often bear the brunt of poverty and limited access to economic opportunities, including unfavourable financial access. Research exists in connection between financial inclusion and women empowerment but most of those are cross-country studies and findings are mixed. Research is scarce for examining the relationship between financial inclusion and women's empowerment. By studying a small village in Bangladesh this paper explored the importance of women’s financial inclusion and showed how far financial inclusion promoted women’s empowerment, and to what extent financial inclusion acted for empowering women of *Gopalpur* village.

1.6 Significance of the Study

Women’s financial inclusion offers the power to change families and societies. Existing research is mostly cross-country studies and findings are mixed. There is a relative dearth of studies examining the nexus of financial inclusion and women empowerment in developing economies, particularly Bangladesh. This study attempted to fill this gap and to achieve the objectives, a survey was conducted on 30 rural women living at *Gopalpur* village of *Netrakona* district. This study tried to identify the key factors for ensuring rural women’s financial services and examine the relationship between financial inclusion and women empowerment.

1.7 Objective of the Study

- To review the present status of women regarding financial inclusion;
- To identify the key factors for ensuring effective financial services for women;
- To examine the relationship between financial inclusion and women's empowerment

2. METHODOLOGY

The major constraint to the effective recognition of women's empowerment and financial inclusion is the scarcity of gender-desegregated data available to technicians, planners, and policymakers. Therefore, the first step towards women's empowerment and financial inclusion is the collection and analysis of gender-desegregated data to understand rural women's present status of access to financial services and the relationship with their empowerment.

2.1 Research Design

The research was an evaluative and descriptive type in nature. Both primary and secondary data sources were the basis of this research which was employed in this study would combine both qualitative and quantitative data. A qualitative method was used to capture data about local perceptions and opinions on the topic using a structured questionnaire. Quantitative data on household ownership, income status, bank account holder, mobile bank account holder, micro-finance borrower, women's role in decision making, their satisfaction about their present status, and other basic information were collected from sample households using a structured questionnaire where I interviewed each woman following the standard administration of interview procedure in this method.

2.2 Sampling Design

The Surveyed village *Gopalpur* was a small village. There were only 43 households in total. Out of 43 households, I interviewed the heads of 30 households. These 30 households were selected randomly following a systematic sampling procedure. Few techniques were applied while selecting households. Such as: while selecting I was conscious about reflecting the ratio

of the total number of Hindus and Muslims population of the village. At the same time, samples were selected from different professions.

2.3 Primary Data Collection

The study was based on both primary and secondary sources of information. Primary data was collected through interviews by structured questionnaire, focus group discussions, and field observations. Secondary data was collected from governmental and non-government organizations. The sources and methods used to acquire data for the research are outlined below.

Most of the data required to answer and validate the research questions was collected from primary sources. To generate the required data from the primary sources, different methodological approaches such as in-depth interviews based on prepared questions, focus group discussions, and field observations were employed. These techniques were used to collect data pertaining household's total annual income, income of the woman interviewed, bank account holder, mobile bank account holder, micro-credit borrower, their role in decision-making in their family, their ability to meet emergencies, and their level of satisfaction with their present status.

Focus group discussion provided an appropriate area to bring together all the women belonging to the target group to share their experiences. Focus group discussions with target groups were held in the village.

Observations of the people's way of life, their assets and resources, the ups and downs to overcoming their daily struggles, their activities for a living, etc, would provide valuable and supportive information. Having a good look at the physical and socio-economic infrastructures, the different economic activities people were involved with and government intervention programs currently undertaken would provide valuable contributions to understanding the existing real situations and the overall situation of women's financial inclusion. Thus, in this study, an attempt was made to carefully observe every situation and understand them fully.

Interviews were an important source of the research information gathering. Yin (2003) identifies two jobs that need to be carried out in the interview process. First, there is a need to follow a line of inquiry, in this case, an "appreciative inquiry", second, ask the actual question in an unbiased manner serving the needs of the line of inquiry. The questions in the interviews

were open-ended and encouraging for unsolicited discussions. The strength of data collection through interviews was that it focused directly on the topic.

2.4 Secondary Data

Secondary data was collected from various government (PKSF) and non-government organizations, individual research papers, and publications.

2.5 Data analysis

After editing and processing, quantitative data were analyzed using mean, median, mode, simple and multiple correlations, regression, and chi-square, and findings were presented in tabular and graphical form. The computer was used in tabulating and processing data.

3 FINDINGS

3.1 Demographic profiles and financial activities

Gopalpur village is a small typical village under *Atpara Upazilla of Netrakona District*. It is an underdeveloped village. The total number of households is 43. The total population is 214. Around 60% of them are Hindus and the rest are Muslims. *Gopalpur* is situated near '*Borobill*' a big hawor which is the main source of irrigation water and fishing for the villagers. For that reason, many of the villagers have taken fishing as an extra source of income. On the other hand, poultry rearing is easier here because the area is rich with natural food for poultry. Most of the people of the village are middle-income and low-income people. A questionnaire was prepared with the line of research for data collection. Women members of the 30 households were interviewed. They were asked 14 questions with some supplementary questions. Out of 30 households, 25 were male-headed households and 5 (five) were female-headed households (Figure-1).

Figure 1. The ratio of male and female-headed households/*Khana* of *Gopalpur*

There are 25 which means 83.3% male-headed households and 5 (16.6%) female-headed households out of surveyed 30 (Fig. 1). Female-headed households were increasing significantly in rural areas in many developing countries as rural males migrated to urban areas due to the lack of employment and other income-generating opportunities.

Figure 2. Income of households

The income of most households (26%) is within the range of 61000 to 70000 (Fig. 2). Because the occupation of the village people was agriculture. Main activities are crop production, poultry, livestock, fishing, homestead vegetable production, etc. Poor farmers had a limited area of land. For that reason, they could not live on cultivation only. In the off-season, some of them worked as day labourers.

Figure 3. Income of rural women

Only one woman had an income above one lac (Fig. 3). She is a teacher at a primary school and the only graduate among the respondents—income of 93% of women within the range of 10000 to 50000. One had no income. She was dependent on her son.

Figure 4. Bank account holders among women

Among 30 women only 10 (33%) women had bank a/c. 67% had no a/c (Fig. 4). The distance of the nearest branch of a bank was 3 k.m. from the village.

Figure-5. Mobile Bank a/c holder among the women

43.3% of women were mobile a/c holders (Fig. 5). Most of them used those mobile a/c only to collect govt. stipend of their children who were going to school.

Figure 6. Micro-Credit Borrower among the women

23.3% of women borrowed money from NGOs and govt. organizations (Fig. 6). The borrowers are using their bank a/c to collect money from the lender.

Figure-7. Access to financial services for women of *Gopalpur* village

10% (3) women of *Gopalpur* village have full access, 23% have partial access and the rest have no access to financial services (Fig. 7).

Figure 8. Micro-credit borrower and bank account holder

Among 30 women 10 had bank a/c and 20 had no a/c (Fig. 8). On the other hand among the a/c holders, 7 were micro-credit borrowers. Women had to open a/c in a bank to collect money as a borrower. It revealed that micro-credit programs increase women's financial inclusion.

Figure 9. Bank a/c holder and Empowerment of women

Among 10 (33.3%) a/c holder women 6 (20%) were empowered which means they could take part in the decision-making of their family. They could make decisions regarding their children's education, daughter's and son's marriage, spending money and savings, etc.

Table 2: Women's taking part in decision-making

<i>Respondents opinion</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	6	20%
No	24	80%
No effect	0	0%

20% of rural women thought that after getting access to financial services they were more able to take part in the decision-making in their family (Table 2). This was an indicator of women's empowerment

Table 3: Ability to meet emergencies

<i>Respondents opinion</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>	<i>%</i>
Yes	9	30%
No	18	60%
No effect	3	10%

30% of rural women thought that after getting access to financial services they were more able to meet the emergencies (Table 3). This was one of the indicators of women's empowerment. It revealed that the microfinance borrowers were mostly women though their empowerment was not up to the mark. From the secondary data collected from PKSf, we could see that among the members and borrowers, 90.36% were women.

Figure 10. Members-Borrowers (million) of PKSF

Members of the POs were at the core of all kinds of field-level operations of PKSF and were organized in groups. As of 30 June 2017, the total number of members of all POs was 12.71 million of which 90.91% were women (Fig. 10). As of 30th June 2017, the number of borrowers was 9.97 million. Out of the total borrowers, the number of women borrowers was 91.85%.

3.2 General challenges

There were so many barriers to entry to economic activities for women outside the home, based on socio-economic attitudes. Women face challenges in coming out of the home to do business as men do. The challenge is changing the attitudes of the people. The following are the findings that were revealed from the study.

Lack of awareness regarding financial services

Most of the women in Gopalpur village were not educated. They were very much unaware of financial services such as bank accounts, and the necessity of their own savings and money transactions. Some of them had a mobile of their own but they only used it to communicate with their family members. Sometimes they received money through B-kash from the members of their families who stayed in cities for employment.. However, they were unaware of continuing transactions and savings.

Limited financial capability and financial literacy

Lack of financial literacy and awareness was a key constraint to accessing and using financial services, with many saying it was the most serious constraint to women's financial inclusion. Surveys conducted by the OECD indicated that, in many countries, women demonstrate less

financial knowledge than men and are also less confident in their financial knowledge and skills. The challenge of improving women's financial capability is compounded by the fact that two-thirds of illiterate people in the world are women.

Low income

Women of Gopalpur were lower-income group people. Most of them were very poor. They depended on agriculture for their livelihood but they had no land or only a few pieces of land for their own. Some of them were day labourers. That's why they did not feel the necessity to open a bank account to save money.

Lack of assets for collateral

In Bangladesh, only a fraction of land is in the hands of women. Women have difficulty in providing immovable collateral given existing land and property rights and cultural norms that discriminate against women. For rural women, limited access to land ownership constrains their ability to provide collateral for loans and therefore limits investment in agricultural inputs and equipment. The expansion of co-titling and individual titling for women is a critically important issue. This scenario prevailed in the village of *Gopalpur* also.

Geographic distance from a financial institution:

The study showed that the distance of the village from the nearest financial institution was 3 km. This was a particular problem in Gopalpur. It was perceived as a barrier for women. The research also indicated that traditionally vulnerable groups such as women and rural populations were less likely to use the formal financial system because of this geographical distance.

Social exclusion

Women are socially and culturally backward. There is an attitude that women do not need any savings of their own because their responsibility goes to their fathers and husbands. Women are the victims of many inequalities due to their social exclusion. This statement was also true for Gopalpur.

Limited access or no access to land ownership

Women of *Gopalpur* village had no land property of their own and they did not even think of having the ownership of land. This was one of the reasons that they had no access or very little

access to financial services. Sometimes they borrowed money from NGOs but could not spend it themselves. Money was being spent by their husbands.

Lack of formal identification:

Women were less likely than men to have formal identification.

Limited ownership of mobile phones and SIM cards

Today, 1.2 billion women in low- and middle-income countries own mobile phones out of a total of 2.9 billion phone owners (41 per cent). Shared usage of mobile phones is also extremely common, including borrowed phones and phones with multiple SIM cards. Similarly, in *Gopalpur* most of the mobile phone owners were male

3.3 Challenges from the Supply Side

Disaggregated data

Financial institutions lack credible gender related. Without the data, financial institutions cannot demonstrate the business case for serving low-income women or have a clear understanding of the female market. Financial institutions are not prepared to develop products for low-income segments due to a lack of information about women's financial needs and financial behaviour.

Risk aversion of banks

Banks are averse to lending to clients without traditional collateral, which women often lack. They are particularly risk-averse to lending to those in the SME and agricultural finance sectors, segments with large percentages of women.

Financial institutions speak a complicated language

This makes it more difficult for women to access products and services, as they are more likely to have low levels of financial education and financial literacy.

Service delivery is not adapted to women

Biases against female customers are common among loan officers, and bank branches are often not a welcoming environment for women. Women report feeling uncomfortable and that they do not belong there. Banks also have limited opening hours and customer outreach does not take women's needs into account.

3.4 Challenges in regulatory and institutional framework

Digital financial services and distribution channels

Digital financial services (DFS) are an effective channel to reach low-income women given their preference for confidentiality, security, and privacy. Regulatory authorities are actively engaged in developing a regulatory framework for DFS and distribution channels, but this has been a challenge since innovation has been outpacing regulation. An enabling interoperability environment must eventually be created for DFS to be an effective channel for women.

Know your customer (KYC) regimes

Most financial institutions are required to follow traditional KYC regimes that require identification and documentation to open accounts, which women in particular do not possess.

Acceptance of discriminatory laws

Women's access to financial services is limited when laws disproportionately favour men, such as inheritance and family laws.

Collateral requirements and collateral registries

While limited progress is being made, regulations on collateral requirements and the absence of registries are still key constraints for women, given the structure of ownership of women's assets.

Credit bureaus

In many developing countries, credit bureaus are uncommon. Where they do exist, financial service providers do not tend to share gender-disaggregated information.

3.5. Internal societal constraints

Women have an abundance of family responsibilities, limited free time, lack of mobility, lower levels of education, and precarious health situations (including maternity-related risks and women placing their own health needs after others). Despite women's vibrant participation in society and their accomplishments, women in general lack decision-making power and confidence, and are impacted by both societal constraints and the demand and supply-side barriers identified above.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

A wide range of surveys should be done by the government to understand the exact scenario of women's financial inclusion in Bangladesh so that appropriate measures can be taken. Collecting financial data disaggregated by gender and conducting policy-related research leads to more informed policy development. Without gender-disaggregated portfolio performance data, there is no evidence to disprove the common perception that women are not credit-worthy. Disaggregating data by gender can also allow institutions to ensure they are reaching their target market.

The development of financial infrastructure is a critically important part of implementing sound policy. The current financial infrastructure does not provide adequate access to an effective retail payments infrastructure (including access to mobile phones). Other financial infrastructure constraints include the lack of collateral registries and credit bureaus; in the latter case, much progress has been made worldwide with the support of the IFC. For that reason, a financial infrastructure building is necessary.

Financial education and financial literacy programs for women are a critical investment in women's financial inclusion. Education and awareness are critical factors in the uptake of any financial service or product and in reducing risks of women, who have less financial capability overall. If they do not feel comfortable using financial services, especially digital financial services will be difficult to close the gender gap. Therefore, financial education and financial literacy programs should be taken for rapid awareness and financial literacy building among women.

Social inclusion of poor women is needed for their financial inclusion. Social inclusion is the provision of certain rights to all women in society, such as women's employment, adequate housing, health care, education and training, etc.

Financing small businesses owned by women can improve women's social inclusion. The development potential of the country's burgeoning micro, small, and medium enterprise (MSME) sector is constrained by low rates of financial access of smaller businesses finding it hard to secure sustainable growth capital.

Digital financial services (DFS) can expand the delivery of basic financial services to the poor through innovative technologies like mobile phone-enabled solutions, electronic money models, and digital payment platforms.

Greater focus on the value proposition of women's financial inclusion, with explicit policy objectives and quantitative targets, can lead to transparent and inclusive policies for women. Although more attention is being given to the value proposition of women's financial inclusion, this has not always translated into explicit policy objectives. With a persistent gender gap, an explicit policy focus on women's financial inclusion is required.

Reforms to legal and regulatory frameworks can create space for innovation that supports greater financial inclusion for women. Legal and regulatory constraints affecting the delivery of financial services and a lack of enabling regulations for the development of the financial system affect women disproportionately. KYC requirements (ID system), lack of data to inform policy, and the acceptance of discriminatory laws relating to women's access to financial services should be reviewed.

Further research may be conducted by selecting a wide area to appraise the importance of a national financial strategy for increasing women's financial inclusion in Bangladesh.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Financial inclusion benefits individuals and households, and well-functioning financial systems benefit the whole country. However, access to financial services is highly unequal, with poor people – and particularly poor women – frequently the least served by existing institutions and systems. There is ample evidence of how financial services of different types can, if properly designed and implemented, enhance women's economic empowerment. This study revealed that financial inclusion increases women's income, purchasing power, living standards, and position in the family. This study also showed that after availing of financial inclusion rural women became able to meet their emergencies, give their children a better education, get better medical facilities, and reduce dependence on local money lenders which means that financial inclusion programmes promote women's economic empowerment. Financial inclusion can therefore help to achieve both gender equity objectives and poverty reduction objectives. To promote poverty reduction and gender equity, there is a clear rationale for using development resources to enhance the financial inclusion of women.

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